

D6.3 – Final report on training, including validation surveys, training assessment recommendations, and lessons learned.

Version 1.0

GA no 952165

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Versioning

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
UT	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS
SISSA	SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE
CINECA	CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO
MPG	MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV
UVSQ	UNIVERSITE DE VERSAILLES SAINT-QUENTIN-EN-YVELINES.
Megware	MEGWARE COMPUTER VERTRIEB UND SERVICE GMBH
TUL	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SRL
IPSAS	FYZIKÁLNY ÚSTAV SLOVENSKEJ AKADÉMIE VIED, v.v.i.
IISAS	ÚSTAV INFORMATIKY SLOVENSKEJ AKADÉMIE VIED, v.v.i.
UPON	UNIVERSITY OF KONSTANZ
CoE	Centre of Excellence
NCC	National Competence Centre
MaX	Materials design at the eXascale
Marvel	National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) MARVEL is a centre on Computational Design and Discovery of Novel Materials created and founded by the Swiss National Science Foundation.
AiiDA	AiiDA is an open-source Python infrastructure to help with automating, managing, persisting, sharing and reproducing the complex workflows associated with modern computational science (supported by the MaX CoE and Marvel).
QMCKl	High-performance quantum Monte Carlo kernel library, one of the main outcomes of the TREX project
TREXIO	Library that defines a standard format for storing wave function parameters, together with a C-compatible API such that it can be easily used in any programming language
ML	Machine Learning
WP#	Work Package with number
SPC	Single Point of Contact
OOD	Operator-On-Duty
VI-HPS	Virtual Institute – High Productivity Supercomputing (https://www.vi-hps.org/)

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Executive summary

The primary mission of the TREX Centre of Excellence (CoE) was development, promotion, maintenance, and application of high-performance software solutions in the field of computational quantum chemistry, physics, materials science, and nanotechnologies to take the full advantage of the upcoming exascale architectures. As a result, a set of selected six massively-parallel quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) and quantum chemistry flagship TREX codes was highly optimized and made user friendly to run efficiently on future-generation supercomputers.

TREX CoE targeted primarily QMC methods which are among the most accurate, albeit also numerically most expensive electronic structure methods. In combination with their uninhibited scaling with the numbers of CPUs and GPUs, it is our strong belief that they have the potential to eventually replace in the next 10-15 years the more established and currently much wider used density functional theory (DFT) and quantum chemistry methods. At this time, though, the QMC community is significantly smaller than both the DFT and quantum chemistry communities and so is also the number of QMC codes available to the community. Hence, in order to enable the future transition towards adoption of the QMC computational paradigm, TREX CoE implemented a very ambitious training and education program to accompany the software solution development.

One of the key pillars of TREX CoE was the training program to foster the use of the developed HPC flagship codes by relevant users and to engage and forge a new generation of highly-skilled computational scientists and software engineers. Part of the training program specifically targeted the youngest generation, i.e. master and PhD. students, as the most effective way to guarantee that the new generation of students acquires the mindset and skills needed for the transition to succeed. The program was addressed in two specific work packages focused jointly on training, education, and users' uptake (WP6) as well as outreach and dissemination of TREX results (WP7). The present document (D6.3) provides a status overview of training and education program for the period M20-M41, i.e. close to the end of the TREX CoE.

In the TREX CoE lifetime WP6 realized five highly successful international workshops for code users in academia and industry, and one for code developers all opened to interested public. For the youngest generation of master and PhD. students TREX CoE organized four Luchon Winter schools. TREX CoE also realized internal training program, opened to public, which took form of four Hackathons addressing the various challenges of the newest- and future-generation supercomputers. Two Hackathons were accompanied by internal events which served the TREX members getting know the progress in flagship code development and the cutting-edge applications. All the codes TREX CoE developed are now publicly available via the TREX web link which also offers support triage.

In the initial stages, up to about M16, WP6 activities requiring personal encounters were heavily affected by the COVID-19 measures, which rendered the organization of training and education, relying on "classical" F2F meetings, more complicated and forced us to adopt on-line training. At around M17, the war in Ukraine started which might have also affected some of the training activities as travel became temporarily not only more expensive but also regarded less safe.

After having realized close to 20 training and education activities, WP6 leaves a deep trace and legacy in the community from the youngest generation to senior scientists from both academia and industry and from code users to code developers. Large body of training material produced by TREX CoE remains on-line for use in the future. TREX managed to gather under its wings the "best heads" in

QMC in Europe. By training and education this unique expertise spread further and we expect it to shape the future of QMC and high-performance computing also long after the project lifetime.

1 Overview of Training and Education

In Section 1.1 the training and education program in the M20-M41 period is outlined. Details of Internal/External training in that period are described in Section 2 / Section 3. The previous training and education program in M1-20 was described in D6.2, see reference in Section 3.1. In addition, Sect. 1.2 provides the information on the core training team and the basic info on the TREX flagship codes and their owners/contact persons. Validation and participants' surveys are compiled in Appendix A.

1.1 Training and Education in the M20-M41 period

TREX training and education strategy as outlined in D6.1 and D6.2 has essentially been followed in the M20-M41 period. At variance with the M1-M20 period where the training activities were heavily affected by the COVID-19 pandemic and outbreak of the war in Ukraine, in the M20-M41 period the direct effect of these factors was subdued to non-existent. However, the more indirect effect was that people became more reluctant to travel and participate in the in-presence activities, compared to the pre-COVID-19 times. The strategy of internal (Section 2) and external (Section 3) training focused on both the code end-users (T6.2) and code developers (T6.4) was implemented with high preference given to practical hands-on training. University education is regarded as one of the most effective ways to guarantee that the new generation of students acquires the expertise needed to become active players in the upcoming radical HPC transformations. This was pursued via T6.3. Alongside with development of our TREX software, implementation of user support triage was implemented (T6.1). All training and education activities are summarized in Table 1. Due to various practical reasons few activities in Table 1 had to be redesigned/reconsidered with respect to the original expectations set in D6.2. ID004, Satellite Hands-on QMC tutorial, had to be replaced by ID021, School on QMC with TurboRVB, because of collision between availability of the TREX lecturers/tutors and the date of proceedings of the CESTC (Central European Symposium on Theoretical Chemistry) symposium to which the Satellite event was originally planned, see D6.2. ID011, HPC Workshop (CECAM), had to be replaced by other activity as outlined in Table 1 as all the available CECAM slots were already taken. ID009 was also replaced by other activity, see Table 1. The Final school (ID005), in collaboration with well-established organizations such as ICTP or CECAM (SISSA has strong links to ICTP and CNRS/Toulouse hosts a CECAM node), and TREX Final event (ID019) have been combined for organisational reasons towards one overarching event, the TREX Symposium “Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations” in Luxembourg in 2024. Contrary, we have been able to add ID008+, the Luchon Winter School in 2024-Q1 and ID021+ - Workshop on QMC Methods at Work for Describing Novel States of Matter, as a linked event to ID021 which TREX CoE had co-organized in 2023-Q3. In addition, in a less formal way, the internal training and education also took place, one example being, for instance, University teaching, as most TREX partners do teach at the European Universities and used this opportunity to transfer their expertise to the university students' curricula, see Section 4.

Table 1: Overview of the realized events. Those described in this document are outlined in green; previous events described in D6.2 are in yellow and those replaced/substituted in orange.

Event ID	Event type	Lead beneficiary	Date	Linked to task	Sept./Page
ID002	QMC Hands-on Workshop	IISAS	Jun-22	T6.2	D6.2
ID006	Winter School	CNRS	Jan-21	T6.3	D6.2
ID007	Winter School	CNRS	Jan-22	T6.3	D6.2
ID012	Hackathon I.	CNRS	Nov-21	T6.4	D6.2
ID013	Hackathon II.	UVSQ	Feb-22	T6.4	D6.2
ID020	e-school on QMC with TurboRVB	SISSA/CNRS	Jul-21	T6.2	D6.2
ID022	CodeRefinery workshop	UVSQ	Nov-20	T6.4	D6.2
ID001	Support Triage	CINECA	Ongoing	T6.1	3.2.1
ID003	Workshop (TUL)	TUL	Apr-23	T6.2	3.2.2
ID005	Final School	LIST/UT	Feb-24	T6.2	3.2.8
ID019	Final Event	LIST/UT	Feb-24	T7.4	3.2.8
ID008	Winter School	CNRS	Jan-23	T6.3	3.2.7
ID008+	Winter School	CNRS	Jan-24	T6.3	3.2.7
ID010	HPC Workshop (II SAS)	IISAS	Jun-23	T6.4	3.2.4
ID014	Hackathon III.	CINECA	Mar-23	T6.4	3.2.5
ID015	Hackathon IV.	MEGWARE	Oct-23	T6.4	3.2.6
ID021	School on QMC with TurboRVB	CNRS	Jul-23	T6.2	3.2.3
ID009	ECNCC event Sweden	UT	Jun-22	T6.3	3.2.9

1.2 TREX Training and Education Core Team

Table 2 lists the core group of TREX consortium members actively involved in WP6, Training and User uptake and Table 3 the TREX flagship codes with the contact points

Table 2: Contact details of members responsible for TREX training and education and their contact-related expertise.

Name	Contact point for expertise
Ivan Štich	WP6 coordinator Contact point of Focus CoE for training; Task leader: Domain-specific and HPC training via education (T6.3); training for code users in academia and industry (T6.2).
Cedric Valensi	Contact points with Focus CoE for training; Expert in online training
Mariella Ippolito	Task leader: Technical Support for use of TREX Codes (T6.1); nucleating a new generation of code developers (T6.4).
Anthony Scemama	Task leader: Domain-specific and HPC training via education (T6.3).
William Jalby	Task leader: Nucleating a new generation of code developers (T6.4) & Academic Training
Nizzolò Zazzeri	Dissemination and outreach for training (WP7)

Table 3: TREX Codes and contact points.

Code	Contact Person
Quantum Package	Anthony Scemama
QMC=Chem	Anthony Scemama
CHAMP	Claudia Filippi
TurboRVB	Michele Casula
GammCor	Kasia Pernal
NECI	Ali Alavi
TREXIO	TREX
QMckI	TREX

2 Internal Training and Education

Since Internal training was described in detail in D6.2 and it did not undergo significant changes, we limit ourselves here to just a brief account. The goal of the internal training and education activities was to ensure that all members of the consortium were able to improve their individual levels of expertise. This was achieved by various types of training, such as kick-off meetings that at initial stages of the project contributed to the internal assessment of training needs of all the TREX members, and their objectives. The same goal was also achieved by the Hackathons, which, as events opened also to public, are described in more detail below. Some TREX institutions have programs in place to encourage and support their employees to continuously develop their personal and professional careers, see D6.2 for more details. Important contribution to Internal training was also Mentoring and Hosting Researchers, in which TREX scientists and software engineers by joining the host groups and institutions were benefiting from the additional local training and supervision expertise. Scientifically fruitful exchange visits had taken place between UT-CNRS/Toulouse, UVSQ-UT, CNRS/Toulouse-UVSQ, CINECA-SISSA, IPSAS-SISSA or CNRS/Paris-IISAS. University education is the most effective way to guarantee that the new generation of students acquires the needed mindset to become active players in the upcoming radical HPC transformations. We were striving to make sure that the TREX expertise made its way to the university curricula of the TREX academia partners in fields such as chemistry, HPC programs, condensed matter physics, and materials science. For instance, the theoretical and hands-on material on QMC we have developed for the Luchon Winter Schools (ID006-ID008+) has been integrated in a new course on Electronic Structure in the Applied Physics program at the UT. For curricula specialized in HPC (such as the 2-year UP Saclay/UVSQ Master program), TREX developed a set of courses illustrating the different key steps in computational science: starting from a theoretical model all the way down to a code able to perform useful computations. Hence, several different approaches are used to solve basically the same problem.

3 External Training and Education

Table 1 summarizes events open to external audiences.

The primary mission of External training and education in events open to external audiences was:

1. creation of awareness on the TREX assets
2. propagation and popularization of the QMC computational paradigm
3. fostering the use of the TREX codes (see Table 3)
4. involvement of the future-generation of HPC ecosystems
5. propagation of results and applications obtained by TREX flagship codes

3.1 Events completed in M01-M19

The events completed between M01-M19 have been described in Public Deliverable D6.2 First report on the status of organisation of training events and activities, including validation surveys which was submitted on 31-08-2022.

3.2 Events completed in M20-M41

Below we have briefly summarized all the relevant details of the events organized since the last deliverable, D6.2. Additional details, including training material, can be found via webpage links on the TREX webpage (<https://trex-coe.eu/events>). Each activity is accompanied by information in nutshell in a tabular form which also gives the web-link to that event. The events are presented so as to cluster together activities with similar target audience, such as, for instance, training focused on code end-users (T6.2), code developers (T6.4) or new generation of students (T6.3). Special category is represented by support triage (T6.1) which will be described as first.

3.2.1 ID001 – Support Triage

The ticketing system developed and described in detail in D6.2 is operational since July 2022. All TREX codes are now fully publicly available via the TREX platform (<https://www.trex-coe.eu/trex-quantum-chemistry-codes>). The NECI, GAMMCOR, QMC = Chem, and Quantum Package are available since July 2022, CHAMP and TurboRVB became publicly available in mid-2023. The technical support triage is meant to complement the support given by the computing centers and other HPC stakeholders (e.g., other CoEs, such as MaX and PoP2, EuroHPC, etc.).

Since the TREX flagship codes became publicly available fairly late in the TREX CoE lifetime the support system was not heavily used so far. The other reason was that the potential TREX code users were often trained directly at the code developers' institutions or in the training and education events, such as, for instance, School(s) on QMC with TurboRVB or Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems and, hence, at this time the users had all the relevant info provided first-hand. We expect this to change in the future when, also due to TREX CoE training and education, the flagship TREX codes are becoming standard and publicly accepted and recognized software.

As an example of the use of the TREX software, Figure 1 gives the statistics for the releases of TREXIO and QMCKI from GitHub with graphs for the period of January 30 – February 2024 and note that the total number of downloads for repo `trex-coe/trexio` since the repository was opened to public was 4492.

Figure 1: Statistics for the releases of TREXIO and QMCKI from GitHub with graphs for the period of January 30 – February 2024

Task Scope	
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake
Event ID	ID001
Task	T6.1
Task Title	Technical support for use of the TREX codes
Task Responsible	Lead: Mariella Ippolito – CINECA
Event Objectives	Description
Users support	Delivers technical and scientific support to the users in a timely manner to troubleshoot and facilitate adoption of the codes.
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level
Code users	Scientists who want to apply the TREX code(s) to systems that present challenge, or face technical problems with code inputs.
HPC Users	Users with problems in using the code(s) on HPC platforms.
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before
Infrastructure	Single Point of Contact, i.e., webpage or mailbox.
Support Team	List of operators in charge of assigning tickets to experts.
Experts List	Anthony Scemama, Claudia Filippi, Michele Casula, Casia Pernal, Ali Alavi
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted
Exploitation of HPC	Maximize the usage of HPC facilities.
Improvement of the production level	Enhance the productivity of researchers by providing timely support.
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/trex-support

3.2.2 ID003 – Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems (TUL)

The workshop took place at the Institute of Physics, Lodz University of Technology, Poland on April 18-20, 2023. The primary purpose of the workshop was to provide insights into both theory and computer implementation of electronic structure methods for strongly correlated (finite) systems which simultaneously require a multireference description and accounting for dynamic correlation. The workshop provided a unique opportunity to familiarize with electronic structure methods for strongly correlated materials and to get insights into their computer implementations via the flagship TREX codes: NECI, Quantum Package, and GammCor. Each workshop session consisted of lectures presenting theoretical backgrounds of the covered methods and tutorials led by the code owners/developers, providing participants with hands-on experience in using codes on HPC platforms. A separate session covered application of machine learning (ML) for predicting molecular properties. In the 3-day workshop 11 expert speakers delivered 9 lecture sessions and 8 tutorial sessions. In the workshop there were 47 registered users and 30 participants. More details, including the training material, can be found on-line: <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-electronic-structure-methods-strong-correlation-theory-computational>. The details of the participants' survey, see A.1 Survey ID003 – Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems (TUL) suggesting that the event was indeed very successful.

Figure 2: Photo of participants of the TUL Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems in Lodz, Poland.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID003	Event Linked	-
Event Title	Workshop TUL	Event Period	2023-Q2
Event Type	Workshop	Event Date	18-20 April 2023
Event Location	TUL	Event Country	Poland
Event Coordinator	Kasia Pernal	Event Organisation	TUL
Event Description	ID003-T6.2 Workshop TUL Poland		
Lecturers/tutors	A. Alawi, P. Lopez, D. Kats (NECI), A. Scemama, E. Giner, P.-F. Loos (Quantum Package), K. Pernal, M. Hapka, L. Veis (GammCor), and M. Rupp (ML).		
Event Scope			
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake		
Task	T6.2		
Task Title	Training for code users in academia and industry		
Task Responsible	Lead: I. Stich – II SAS; M. Casula – CNRS		
Event Objectives	Description		
Training in Quantum chemistry	Practical electronic structure course with focus on Quantum chemistry methods using GammCor, Quantum Package, and NECI codes in molecular science augmented by applications of ML methods.		
Machine Learning	Focus on how to use the TREX platform together with the machine learning (ML) tools in the domain of molecular science.		
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level		
Code users	PhD. student and post-docs primarily but also more senior code users. Registered number of participants: 47		
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before		
Code interface	The universal TREXIO library operable with TREX codes (GammCor/Quantum Package/NECI) and debugged for the tasks described in event objectives		
Preliminary knowledge	Basic knowledge of quantum chemistry methods, basic understanding and skills in running quantum chemistry calculations.		
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted		
More users of TREX codes	Participants able to use a set of TREX quantum chemistry codes and their interfaces. They will learn about the capabilities of the codes.		
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-electronic-structure-methods-strong-correlation-theory-computational		

3.2.3 ID021 – TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB (SISSA),

The event took place at SISSA, Trieste, Italy on July 3-7, 2023. The school followed the well proven format of the previous school(s), such as the ID020 which took place in 2021. The main difference being that the 2023 school was not an e-school but an all in-presence event. The lectures covered topics such as probability and sampling, MC sampling and Markov chains, variational wavefunction and optimization, QMC ionic forces, diffusion Monte Carlo. The hands-on tutorials focused on the TurboRVB code, TurboGenius, and TurboWorkflows, with applications for both molecular and periodic systems. In the 5-day workshop altogether 14 lecture sessions and 8 hands-on sessions were delivered by 7 expert speakers. The event also had a poster session. There were 62 registered users and 27 participants. More details, including the training material, can be found on-line: <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-electronic-structure-methods-strong-correlation-theory-computational>. A.2 Survey ID021 TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB (SISSA) details the participants' survey, suggesting that the event was, similarly to the previous edition(s) very successful.

Figure 3: Participants of the TREX workshop in the supervised hands-on training.

Figure 4: Photo of participants of the TREX workshop.

In line with this TREX School a joint effort was done on the *Workshop on Quantum Monte Carlo Methods at Work for Describing Novel States of Matter*, organized by ICTP, Trieste, Italy on July 10-14, 2023 and co-organized by TREX CoE in honor and memory of our late colleague, Prof. Sandro Sorella, see <https://indico.ictp.it/event/10187>. Large part of the TREX school participants also took part in the workshop.

Figure 5: Collective photo of participants of the ICTP workshop on “Quantum Monte Carlo Methods at Work for Describing Novel States of Matter” co-organized by TREX.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID021	Event Linked	ID021+
Event Title	TREX school on QMC with TurboRVB	Event Period	2023-Q3
Event Type	Workshop	Event Date	July 3-7, 2023
Event Location	Trieste, Italy	Event Country	Italy

Event Coordinator	Michele Casula	Event Organisation	SISSA
Event Description	ID021-T6.2 Workshop SISSA, Italy		
Lecturers/tutors	M. Casula, K. Nakano, and S. Moroni/ K. Nakano, O. Kohulak, A. Raghav, G. Tenti, A. Paavo Seitsonen , T. Gorni, and M. Casula.		
Event Scope			
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake		
Task	T6.2		
Task Title	Training for code users in academia and industry		
Task Responsible	Lead: – SISSA; S. Moroni – SISSA		
Event Objectives	Description		
Basic QMC training	Crash-course in practical electronic structure QMC theory and computations (14 lecture sessions).		
Basic TREX code/s hands-on training	Practical entry-level QMC hands-on sessions using TurboRVB TREX code. VMC, DMC, for molecules, solids in the domain of molecular and materials science. (8 hands-on sessions).		
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level		
Code users	Audience: MSc. and PhD students, postdocs, researchers Entry level: electronic structure-interested students/researchers with proven experience in DFT, quantum/physical chemistry, computational materials science, condensed matter or computational physics, etc.		
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before		
codes ready for use	TurboRVB codes debugged for the tasks described in event objectives.		
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted		
Increased QMC awareness	Most of the expected participants did not have any experience with QMC. Their participation has increased the number of "QMC-aware" people.		
New QMC users	Increased number of QMC users thanks to participation in the school, that have not been using QMC in their research before.		
More TREX code users	More inexperienced users got chance to interact with TREX codes, participants already using QMC in their research got chance to find better solutions for their research.		
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-school-qmc-turborvb-2023		

3.2.4 ID010 – HPC Workshop “Code Tuning for the Exascale”

The event took place at the SAS campus in Bratislava, Slovakia at the Institute of Materials and Machine Mechanics on June 5-9, 2023. Slovakia was selected on purpose for this event as a country currently advancing its HPC ecosystem. Since this was an event targeting code developers, the local organizer, IISAS, approached, in addition to UVSQ as the TREX partner expert also the NCCs in Slovakia and in the neighboring countries (Czech Republic and Austria) which contributed the 3-day program. The first day program was delivered by the NCC Austria and was focused on Advanced parallel programming, i.e. MPI+OpenMP+OpenMP offloading, NUMA architectures and specially pinning. In the hands-on labs the effects of affinity and pinning on performance was demonstrated. The second day program was delivered by the NCC Czech Republic which provided an introduction to the fundamental concepts of parallel application performance analysis, power consumption measurement, and energy efficiency evaluation in HPC systems including monitoring and control of power and energy dissipation. The practical aspect of these principles was shown in the hands-on sessions. The last day was a TREX day and the program was delivered by the UVSQ. The major performance bottlenecks when optimizing an application were reviewed and analyzed at the node level: vectorization, code quality, locality and parallelism. MAQAO/ONE View performance analysis tools (www.maqao.org) which can detect such bottlenecks and assess quantitatively their performance impact were introduced for an efficient optimization strategy. Data from TREX applications were used in the presentations. In the hands-on sessions attendees could test on their codes with the MAQAO/ONE View toolset under the supervision of the toolset developers. Altogether in the 3-day workshop 10 lecture sessions and 12 hands-on sessions were delivered by 8 expert speakers. There were 22 registered users and 16 participants in the workshop, large part of which were Slovak nationals. More details, including the lectures and training material, can be found on-line (<https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-code-tuning-exascale>). A.3 Survey ID010 TREX HPC Workshop: Code Tuning for the Exascale (IISAS) details the participants’ survey, which suggest that the event was successful and served the intended purpose well.

Figure 6: Photo of participants of the HPC Workshop “Code Tuning for the Exascale” in Bratislava, Slovakia.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID010	Event Linked	-
Event Title	Code tuning for the Exascale	Event Period	2023-Q2
Event Type	Workshop	Event Date	June 5-7, 2023
Event Location	Bratislava	Event Country	Slovakia
Event Coordinator	Ivan Stich	Event Organization	II SAS, EuroCC/NSCC
Event Description	ID010-T6.4 HPC workshop at SAS campus in Bratislava, Slovakia		
Event Scope			
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake		
Task	T6.4		
Task Title	Nucleating a new generation of code developers		
Task Responsible	Lead: I. Stich – II SAS; W. Jalby – UVSQ		
Event Objectives	Description		
Increasing HPC literacy	Increase HPC literacy in techniques of advanced parallelization, performance and code efficiency analysis. (3 full days)		
Lecturers/tutors	Prof. C. Blaas-Schenner, I. Vialov, TU Wien, T. Panoc, O. Vysocký, R. Vavřík, M. Špeřko, TU Ostrava, W. Jalby, C. Valensi, UVSQ		
Code Developers	Code Developers taking advantage from this event learning computational techniques and programming models that improve the quality of their codes, their performance and the optimal exploitation of the computational resources		
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before		
Programming	A good knowledge of C and/or Fortran and/or C++ was required and a basic knowledge of MPI, OpenMP and CUDA strongly recommended		
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted		
Increased HPC literacy	Improved programming skills, HPC literacy, and more effective user software		
Optimal usage of CPU resources	Optimal, more efficient, exploitation of the computational resources on pre-exascale & exascale platforms		
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-code-tuning-exascale		

3.2.5 ID014 – Hackathon III, The “GPUs Hackathon”

The event took place at CINECA at Dipartimento HPC, Bologna, Italy on March 6-8, 2023. The Hackathon was specifically targeting TREX code developers to port their codes onto GPUs, or optimize their applications that already run on GPUs. With the GPUs now part of almost every supercomputer, this is an enormously important agenda and all TREX flagship codes have already been or are in process of porting onto GPUs. All lectures were given by Nvidia and Intel experts. The hands-on exercise was also supervised by the Nvidia and Intel experts on the local Marconi100 supercomputer equipped with Nvidia cards. The GPU porting was focusing OpenACC and OpenMP offload. Day one was dedicated mainly to theoretical sessions on GPU programming paradigms, while the remaining two days were dedicated to practical hands-on sessions. The Hackathon was a unique opportunity to learn more about the code porting to GPUs and improvement of performance and portability using GPUs. The number of participants in this internal event was 10, two Intel and Nvidia experts, and a CINECA representative.

Figure 7: Participants visiting the Marconi100 machine room.

Figure 8: Photo of participants of the Hackathon III at CINECA, Bologna, Italy.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID014	Event Linked	-
Event Title	TREX hackathon III.	Event Period	2023-Q1
Event Type	Hackathon	Event Date	March 6-8, 2023
Event Location	Bologna	Event Country	Italy
Event Coordinator	M. Ippolito, W. Jalby	Event Organisation	CINECA / UVSQ
Event Description	ID014-T6.4 Hackathon		
Lecturers/tutors	M. Bettencourt- Nvidia, G. Rossi – Intel, D. Molinari - Cineca		
Event Scope			
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake		
Task	T6.4		
Task Title	Nucleating a new generation of code developers		
Task Responsible	Lead: W. Jalby – UVSQ; M. Ippolito – CINECA		
Event Objectives	Description		
Tuning QMCKl and QMC codes	The attendees learned how to tune their codes on heterogeneous platforms with GPUs or improve their performance if they already have been ported.		
Learning how to use supercomputer with GPUs	The attendees learned the features of the Marconi100 supercomputer equipped with Nvidia cards and how to use the platform to achieve best performance.		
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level		
Code owners, experienced users, and technologists	The hackathon involved code users, developers and HPC technologists. Supervised by the Nvidia/Intel experts they learned the craft of tuning the QMC flagship codes to achieve the best performance on a heterogeneous machine with GPUs.		
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before		
Code knowledge	All the participants were supposed to be familiar with the fundamentals of high-level programming languages and parallel computing.		
Impact after event	Improved expertise in GPU programming paradigms and GPU porting via OpenACC and OpenMP offload.		
Exploitation of HPC resources	Testing the improved scalability via engagement of Nvidia GPUs, including QMC flagship codes and QMCKl on the Marconi100 platform.		
Success story	Ability to run challenging calculations on one of the most powerful machines in Europe at the time of the event and possibly on even more powerful in the future.		
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-hackathon-iii		

3.2.6 ID015 – Hackathon IV - MAQAO/ONE

The event took place at the Megware Benchmark Center in Chemnitz, Germany, October 16-20, 2023. This Hackathon was targeting a more mixed community of both the TREX code developers as well as researchers in applications of QMC computational techniques. In the former, given the importance of code quality in numerically extremely expensive algorithms such as QMC, the MAQAO/ONE View performance analysis tools (www.maqao.org) were once again reviewed and applied to the flagship TREX codes targeting the major performance bottlenecks when optimizing an application and analyzed at the node level: vectorization, code quality, locality and parallelism. Since Megware is a benchmarking center, the local HPC clusters were used for that purpose. The lecture and demonstration by an Intel Research Engineer, also targeted TREX code developers by presenting AI-driven computer code generation. The flagship TREX code Quantum Package was used for that purpose.

In applications of QMC computational techniques a detailed account of ML potentials was presented. ML potentials is a very important development which found its way also into QMC methods as it makes it possible to obtain fixed-node QMC-quality atomic forces for molecular dynamics or path integral simulations simply by sampling the potential energy surfaces. A range of such method variants were presented, such as linear and kernel models and neural networks. Their relative strengths and weaknesses were discussed and an application on thermal conductivity of zirconia via Kubo-Greewood formula was shown.

Figure 9: Photo of participants of the Hackathon IV in Chemnitz, Germany.

Figure 10: Photo of participants gathering for the 1-day TREX event at ODC of in Chemnitz, Germany.

The number of participants in this event was 12.

Hackathon IV was connected with an internal 1-day TREX event at the ODC center at the city center. The presentations were followed by two members of the Advisory board, Michel Masella and Eric Petit. Each WP leader made an account of the progress in the given activity. Results of selected applications (WP5) were also presented (M. Casula, K. Pernal, I. Stich...). The number of participants in this event was 15 plus two Advisory board members.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID015	Event Linked	1-day internal TREX event
Event Title	TREX Hackathon IV.	Event Period	2023-Q4
Event Type	Hackathon	Event Date	October 16-20 2023
Event Location	Chemnitz	Event Country	Germany
Event Coordinator	A. Auweter	Event Organisation	Megware
Event Description	ID015-T6.4 Hackathon		
Lecturers/tutors	W. Jalby, Eric Petit, M. Rupp /C. Valensi		
Event Scope			
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake		
Task	T6.4		
Task Title	Nucleating a new generation of code developers		
Task Responsible	Lead: W. Jalby – UVSQ; A. Auweter		
Event Objectives	Description		
Demonstrate performance of TREX software on state-of-the-art HPC systems	This event took place at a late stage of the project and served as a final opportunity for code optimization.		
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level		
Code owners and developers	12 code owners and developers at the Hackathon and 15 + two Advisory board members at the internal event		
HPC experts from HPC data centers and HPC technology providers (e.g., Intel)	4 HPC experts		
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before		
Sufficient number of HPC experts	The ratio of HPC experts to support participating code owners and developers was \approx 1:3 ratio		
Access to machines	Local HPC cluster(s) were pre-installed online and ready to use on-line from the event venue		
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted		
Increased efficiency	Publicly available software running efficiently on state-of-the-art HPC systems & its efficient use		
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-hackathon-iv		

3.2.7 ID006 – ID007 – ID008 – ID008+ Winter schools

This series of activities targets the youngest audience, master and 1st-year PhD students, and has the form of satellite events to the Luchon Winter School of the Erasmus Mundus Joint European Master Degree program in Theoretical Chemistry and Computational Modelling. These include lectures in theoretical foundations as well as hands-on experience using mostly simplified educational atomic/molecular codes. The students are encouraged to choose a QMC project and write a simple QMC code by themselves, such as a He atom or H₂ molecule and compute the ground-state energies. The event in 2023 (ID008) was organized on Jan. 28 – Feb. 3 2023. The event attracted 40+ students, 8 of which chose the QMC project. Since the TREX project was extended by 6 months it also covers the 2024 Luchon winter school which TREX joint in the proven format, labelled ID008+. In 2024 35 students registered for the event, but 3 could not join due to visa delay. 15 students chose the QMC project (one-day tutorial : 3.5 hours, see <https://trex-coe.github.io/qmc-ltcc-2023>, in the morning, 2.5 hours in the afternoon).

Figure 11: Photo of participants of the Luchon winter school, Aspet, France.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID006 – ID007 – ID008 Winter schools	Event Linked	-
Event Title	Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry	Event Period	2023-Q1 2024-Q1
Event Type	Satellite Event	Event Date	28. Jan. – 3. Feb. 27. Jan. – 2. Feb.
Event Location	Aspet	Event Country	France
Event Coordinator	Claudia Filippi, Anthony Scemama	Event Organisation	
Event Description	ID006-T6.3 Satellite Event Luchon Winter School Erasmus Mundus		
Lecturers/tutors	A. Scemama/A. Scemama, A. Ammar, V. Gopal Chilkuri, O. Kohulak		

Event Scope	
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake
Task	T6.3
Task Title	Domain-specific and HPC training via education
Task Responsible	Lead: A. Scemama – CNRS; I. Stich – II SAS
Event Objectives	Description
Basic QMC Training	The “Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry” Luchon Winter School focus on the computer implementation of methods in quantum chemistry. The tutorials include: Advanced programming techniques; Geometry and Topology: Building Nanoparticles; Low-dimensional Carbon structures: the usefulness of simple approaches; Quantum Magnetism: the Heisenberg model; Quantum Dynamics: Propagating wave packets; Vibrations in Molecules: Harmonic/Morse Oscillators. TREX participated by teaching one extra day to introduce the basic concepts of QMC methods and to explain the art of writing a simple QMC program.
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level
Students	Audience: master students and 1 st -year PhD students Number of participants: 40+ /32 participants.
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before
Background	Basic knowledge of programming. Basic knowledge in quantum chemistry.
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted
Increased number of students interested in electronic structure	Democratization of QMC methods. If QMC is learned at the master’s degree, it will be considered by young researchers as a well-established method and not as an exotic method for a small community of experts.
Related Document	Description
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/luchon-winter-school

3.2.8 ID005 - Final Symposium “Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations”

The original scope of ID005 Final school and ID019 Final Event are combined to a Final Symposium.

The aim of this event was to promote the use of all flagship TREX codes within academia and industry and thus significantly enlarge the QMC user community. In order to increase the impact of the event, the final school was merged with the Final Event in one overarching event, the Symposium “Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations”, the rationale being to offer the participants contact with the best people in QMC from both sides of the Atlantic. To this end, 29 experts accepted the invitation to lecture in the event of which 10 were TREX partners. The presentations were a blend of talks focusing on the QMC techniques, their application, code efficiency, code optimization techniques, and HPC exascale technologies as such. The presentations included representatives of the EuroHPC, as well as representatives of the counterparts of the TREX CoE in the U.S.A., such as the Computational Materials Sciences (CMS), Center for Predictive Simulation of Functional Materials (CPSFM), and the Exascale Computing Project (ECP). Ample space was given to informal contacts, such as round tables. The training impact was amplified by a number of junior people from TREX partners’ groups.

Figure 12: Project Coordinator, Claudia Filippi introducing the TREX CoE.

Figure 13: Anouar Benali introducing the U.S. computational initiative, the QMCPACK code, CPSFM, and ECP.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID005	Event Linked	ID019
Event Title	Final School	Event Period	February 2024
Event Type	Final School	Event Date	5.-9. 2. 2024
Event Location	ICTP or CECAM	Event Country	Luxembourg
Event Coordinator	Claudia Filippi	Event Organization	-
Event Description	ID005-T6.2 Final School in Luxembourg		

Event Scope	
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake
Task	T6.2
Task Title	Training for code users in academia and industry
Task Responsible	Lead: Matthias Rupp - LIST, C. Filippi - UT
Event Objectives	Description
Training in TREX software and methodology and beyond	The school/symposium focused on a wide range of topics, such as the QMC techniques, their application, code efficiency, code optimization techniques, and HPC exascale technologies as such. Various software's were introduced, including the flagship TREX codes and libraries (QMCKI, TREXIO) together with the ML tools and the workflow structure integrated in AiiDA. The U.S. counterpart, such as the QMCPACK and ML software was also discussed and showcased.
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level
Code users	≈80 participants. PhD students, postdocs, and researchers in academia and industry.
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before
General field-specific knowledge	Background in electronic structure theory
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted
Increased use of TREX HPC software.	Promote the use of TREX codes within academia and industry; significantly enlarge user community; foster use of HPC codes.
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/bridging-quantum-monte-carlo-and-high-performance-simulations

3.2.9 ID011 - Workshop ENCCS

We are pleased to announce the 10th edition of the OpenMolcas developers' workshop, bringing together the community of developers, users, and anyone else interested in the project. This year the workshop is hosted by the Quantum Chemistry Group at Uppsala University and we are very excited to announce that we have partnered up with TREX and ENCCS, which will help us with the organization, but most importantly will contribute to the scientific part as well!

We invite everyone to join us here in sunny Uppsala, where the workshop will take place, but we understand that in these uncertain times it might still be difficult to travel. No worries, the workshop is offered in a hybrid format, and anyone who registers is able to participate exclusively online.

Event Overview			
Event ID	ID011	Event Linked	-
Event Title	Openmolcas-2022	Event Period	2022
Event Type	Workshop	Event Date	8-10 Juni
Event Location	CECAM node	Event Country	Sweden
Event Coordinator	C. Filippi	Event Organisation	UT
Event Description	ID011-T6.4 Workshop node		

Event Scope	
Work Package	WP6 Training and user uptake
Task	T6.4
Task Title	Training for code users in academia and industry
Task Responsible	Lead: C. Filippi - UT
Event Objectives	Description
Training in TREX software and methodology	Various software's were introduced, including the flagship TREX codes and libraries (QMckl, TREXIO) together with the ML tools and the workflow structure integrated in AiiDA. T
Event Target Audience	Description of audience and expected number of participants, entry level
Code users	PhD students, postdocs, and researchers in academia and industry.
Pre-Requirements	Detail what is required before
General field-specific knowledge	Background in electronic structure theory
Impact after event	Detail what impact is targeted
Increased use of TREX HPC software.	Promote the use of TREX codes within academia and industry; significantly enlarge user community; foster use of HPC codes.
Web link	https://trex-coe.eu/events/bridging-quantum-monte-carlo-and-high-performance-simulations https://enccs.github.io/openmolcas-2022/program/

4 Impact of Training and Education events

The outcomes, results, and consequences of the TREX training and education events and actions implemented in WP6 are briefly summarized in Table 4. Essentially 3 different groups “trainees” were targeted: code users, code developers, and undergraduate/graduate students in the form of workshops, hackathons, and winter schools. Perhaps the most important outcome is related to use of the software developed and maintained by the TREX consortium which also provides support triage to the code users.

Table 4: Brief Summary of the actual outcomes of the TREX training and education program in the period M20-M41.

Type	Explanation
TREX code user uptake	Increased number of TREX users via events (schools, workshops, satellite events, hands-on sessions): 30 end-users have been trained with TurboRVB experience (ID021), lectures plus hands-on experience; 27 end-users have been trained with methods and codes for strong correlation (NECI, QP, GammCor), including hands-on experience (ID003). In 7 events (ID003, ID006, ID007, ID008, ID010, ID014, ID015, ID021) TREX software was used as a teaching/training tool.
TREX code developer’s uptake	HPC workshop (ID010) on advanced parallelization techniques, parallel applications performance analysis and general code optimization using MAQAO/ONE View tool, including hands-on experience organized in a country advancing its HPC ecosystem (Slovakia) with 16 participants. Two Hackathons (ID013, ID014) organized one on GPUs parting/use (ID013) with 10 participants, including hands-on experience on Marconi100 and one on general code optimization using MAQAO/ONE View tool and on AI-assisted programming, including hands-on experience with 12 participants.
Increased literacy in HPC and awareness in high-accuracy quantum simulations and codes	Broad outreach to user communities also in countries advancing their HPC ecosystem; QMC as an accurate quantum method ready for exascale received more attention via training and education via two hands-on workshops (ID003 and ID021). and HPC workshop (ID010) organized in Slovakia with still critically underdeveloped HPC ecosystem is expected to be a game changer with $\approx 80\%$ of participants being locals. Communication and dissemination channels for creating awareness were addressed by WP7 increased the impact further.
Higher and effective use of current and upcoming HPC infrastructures	Most of the electronic structure software (DFT, GW, quantum chemistry) is not suited for the challenges posed by the upcoming HPC infrastructure. TREX training and education program promoting the stochastic QMC alternatives has significantly changed the situation via the code user (ID003, ID021) and code developer (ID010, ID013, ID014) uptake. These and TREX events already did enlarge the pool of experienced users and developers of stochastic quantum software ready for future-generation of HPC infrastructure.

5 Conclusions

To conclude, document D6.3 provides an overview of the general training and education strategy implementation within WP6 and of its achievements in the second half of the project lifetime. This covers the different audience types, overview of events with a timeline, and a detailed account of all training and education events completed in the period of M20-M41.

WP6 in the TREX CoE lifetime organized close to 20 training/education events and generated a huge body of training material available on-line. The events included 5 schools/workshops for code users, one for code developers, four hackathons and four winter schools for the youngest generation of master and PhD. students. All the events were met with an enormous enthusiasm both on the side of participants and organizers alike. The true highlight was the final event Symposium “Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations” linked with the final school which, in addition to the TREX CoE participants and interested community, was able to attract two dozens of the best QMC experts and speakers from Europe and overseas.

While the TREX CoE ends in its current form, its legacy in the form of strengthening the QMC community enlarged by intense training and education, the links between the major QMC players in Europe and beyond deepened by TREX, the flagship codes developed and fine-tuned by TREX software engineers, and the on-line training material will persist.

A Appendix Validation of completed events

For a selected subset of events (ID003, ID021, and ID010) an explicit validation, including participants' surveys after the event, was conducted. The events were selected so as to reflect the wide variety of the communities WP6 was addressing. ID003 was focusing on molecular systems and their solution using quantum chemistry methods. ID021 targeted more the extended systems and their treatment via stochastic QMC methods, while ID010 was intended for code developers. The validation and surveys were done by TRUST-IT as a part of the WP7 activities.

A.1 Survey ID003 – Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems (TUL)

❖ **General information:**

- ✚ 3-day workshop
- ✚ 9 lecture sessions
- ✚ 8 tutorial hands-on sessions
- ✚ 11 expert speakers
- ✚ 3 TREX codes
(NECI, QP, GammCor)

✚ **Participants**

- ✚ 47 registered users
- ✚ 30 participants

✚ **Countries represented: 14**

- ✚ Poland: 16
- ✚ Germany: 5
- ✚ Czech Republic: 3

✚ **Stakeholder Type**

- ✚ 89,4% Universities and Res. Inst.
- ✚ 10,6% Res. & Innovation projects

✚ **Gender**

- ✚ 72% ♂
- ✚ 28% ♀

Satisfaction survey (22 Respondents; 90 person days)

Q1: The event was

Q2: Did the organizers sustain interest and participation?

Q3: Lectures and hands-on sessions explanatory and interesting?

Q4: Content of the event relevant?

Q5: Expectations fulfilled?

A.2 Survey ID021 TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB (SISSA)

❖ **General information:**

- ✚ 5-day workshop
- ✚ 14 lecture sessions
- ✚ 8 tutorial hands-on sessions
- ✚ 7 expert speakers
- ✚ 1 TREX code (TurboRVB)
- ✚ 1 poster session

❖ **Participants**

- ✚ 62 registered users
- ✚ 27 participants

❖ **Countries represented: 13**

- ✚ Italy: 8
- ✚ India: 4
- ✚ France: 2

❖ **Stakeholder Type**

- ✚ 100% Universities and Res. Inst.

❖ **Gender**

- ✚ 90% ♂
- ✚ 10% ♀

Satisfaction survey (15 Respondents; 120 person days)

Q1: The event was

Q2: Did the organizers sustain interest and participation?

Q3: Lectures and hands-on sessions explanatory and interesting?

Q4: Content of the event relevant?

Q5: Expectations fulfilled?

A.3 Survey ID010 TREX HPC Workshop: Code Tuning for the Exascale (IISAS)

❖ **General information:**

- ✚ 3-day workshop
- ✚ 10 lecture sessions
- ✚ 12 tutorial hands-on sessions
- ✚ 8 expert speakers

❖ **Participants**

- ✚ 22 registered users
- ✚ 16 participants

❖ **Countries represented: 3**

- ✚ Slovakia: 13
- ✚ Czech Republic: 2
- ✚ Slovenia: 1

❖ **Stakeholder Type**

- ✚ 86,4% Universities and Res. Ins.
- ✚ 9,1% Res. & Innovation projects
- ✚ 4,5% Centers of Excellence on HPC

❖ **Gender**

- ✚ 90% ♂
- ✚ 10% ♀

Satisfaction survey (9 Respondents; 48 person days)

Q1: The event was

Q2: Did the organizers sustain interest and participation?

Q3: Lectures and hands-on sessions explanatory and interesting?

Q4: Content of the event relevant?

Q5: Expectations fulfilled?

